

Physico-Chemical Studies of the Complexes of Cu(II) with Some α -Amino-oxy Acids

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pH-metric and conductometric studies of the complexes formed by Cu(II) with α -amino-oxy acids in aqueous medium at 0.2 M ionic strength reveal the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. The stability constants of the complexes formed were computed by the Calvin and Melchior method. The Cu(II) complexes of 2-amino-oxy acetic, propionic, butyric and isobutyric acid hydrobromides have $\log \beta_1$ values of 6.79, 6.44, 6.51 and 6.77, respectively and $\log \beta_2$ values of 11.90, 11.96, 12.68 and 11.81, respectively at $30 \pm 1^\circ$.

α -AMINO-OXY acids are important biologically active compounds. Some α -amino-oxy derivatives have antitubercular activity¹. Use of amino-oxy acetate as a transaminase inhibitor in the gluconeogenesis in the cortex of guinea pig kidney has been studied². However, metal complexes of α -amino-oxy acids have not yet been examined. We now report the measurements on the dissociation constants of some α -amino-oxy acids and the stability of their complexes with Cu(II).

Experimental

The α -amino-oxy acid hydrobromides were prepared by the method of Malkani³. Other reagents used were of AnalaR grade. Solutions were prepared in double distilled, air free water. Fresh solutions of reagents were always used to avoid the effect of age and hydrolysis.

Titration procedures :

A Systronic 324 pH-meter with accuracy of ± 0.01 pH unit was used for pH titrations. The pH meter was calibrated with buffer solutions of pH 4.0 and 7.0 at $30 \pm 1^\circ$. The linearity of the glass electrode was checked at intervals with standard buffers. Definitive proton and metal stability constants were obtained by titrating solutions (20 ml) of the appropriate α -amino-oxy acid hydrobromide, in presence and absence of Cu(II) ions, with sodium hydroxide in glass vessels maintained at $30 \pm 1^\circ$. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.2 M with KNO_3 .

Determination of acid dissociation constants :

The pH titration of hydrobromide of a α -amino-oxy acid (20 ml) of known strength was carried out to determine the acid dissociation constants of the α -amino-oxy acid.

The results of a typical titration are given in Fig. 1. The degree of formation of the ligand proton complexes, \bar{n}_H , and the dissociation constants of the

Fig. 1. (a) Titration of α -amino-oxy propionic acid hydrobromide (20 ml 1.0×10^{-2} M) with 0.5 N NaOH solution $\mu = 0.1$ M; (b) Titration of α -amino-oxy propionic acid hydrobromide in presence of copper(II) nitrate with 0.5 N NaOH [20 ml 1.0×10^{-2} M α -amino-oxy propionic acid hydrobromide + 0.5×10^{-2} M copper (II) nitrate] $\mu = 0.1$ M.

TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF α -AMINO-OXY PROPIONIC ACID

pH	2.65	2.73	2.78	2.84	2.92	3.00
\bar{n}_H	1.776	1.760	1.784	1.716	1.680	1.650
pK ₁	3.20	3.22	3.22	3.24	3.24	3.26
pH	11.15	11.30	11.40	11.50	11.55	11.65
\bar{n}_H	0.750	0.700	0.650	0.600	0.550	0.500
pK ₂	11.63	11.67	11.67	11.67	11.64	11.65

corresponding acid were calculated by the Irving and Rossotti method⁴. The results are given in Table 1, where pH values have been interpolated from a large scale graph.

The average value of pK_1 is 3.24 (± 0.02) and that of pK_2 is 11.65 (± 0.02).

The apparatus and procedure were checked by determining the dissociation constants of glycine by pH titration of glycine hydrobromide with NaOH solution which gave $pK_1=2.30$ and $pK_2=10.00$ which agree fairly well with the values (2.27 and 9.86) reported by Irving and Pettit⁵.

Determination of metal-ligand stability constant :

A known concentration (C_L) of the appropriate α -amino-oxy acid hydrobromide was titrated in the absence and presence of a known concentration (C_M) of Cu(II) ions (Fig. 1). The ratio of $C_L : C_M$ was 2 : 1 to favour the formation of complexes of formula ML_2 . The degree of formation of the metal complexes, \bar{n} , was calculated from the titration curves (Fig. 1) by Calvin and Melchior method⁶ and the values of the free ligand exponent, pL , were obtained by the equation

$$pL = \log 10 \frac{\{1 + [H^+]/K_1 + [H^+]^2/K_1K_2\}}{(C_L - \bar{n}C_M)}$$

where K_1 and K_2 are the first and the second dissociation constants of the given α -amino-oxy acid. During the titration precipitation occurs at pH 8.0. Therefore \bar{n} and pL values were calculated for points below the precipitation point. Stability constants were calculated from the equation to the straight line

$$\frac{\bar{n}}{(2-\bar{n})} \cdot \frac{1}{[L^-]^2} = \frac{(1-\bar{n})}{(2-\bar{n})} \cdot \frac{\beta_1}{[L^-]} + \beta_2$$

The best values of the gradient β_1 and intercept β_2 were calculated by the method of least square. The results of a typical experiment are given in Table 2.

TABLE-2

Initial volume : 20 ml ; Temp. = $30 \pm 1^\circ$; $C_L = 0.01 M$, $C_M = 0.005 M$; $\mu = 0.2 M$; strength of alkali = $0.5 M$

pH	6.00	6.25	6.46	6.68	6.80	7.00	7.20	7.40
\bar{n}	0.065	0.100	0.150	0.225	0.250	0.350	0.500	0.625
pL	7.67	7.40	7.20	7.00	6.89	6.72	6.56	6.40
pH	7.60	7.80	8.00					
\bar{n}	0.800	0.860	0.950					
pL	6.35	6.07	5.91					

The formation curve for the complex constructed from the stability constants is shown in Fig. 2.

Calculated values of acid dissociation constants and metal stability constants are summarised in Table 3 along with the values for the corresponding amino acids⁵.

Conductometric titrations :

Conductometric titrations were carried only by means of Systronic type 305 conductometer.

Fig. 2. Plot of \bar{n} as a function of pL in case of Cu(II) + α -amino-oxy propionic acid.

TABLE-3

Ligand	I	Ia*	II	IIa*	III	IV	IVa*
$pK_1(H_2L^+)$	3.68	2.24	3.24	(2.90)	3.39	3.35	(2.35)
$pK_2(HL^+)$	11.43	(9.86)	11.65	(9.93)	12.08	12.05	(10.25)
Cu(II) complexes							
$\log \beta_1$	6.79	(8.12)	6.44	(8.15)	6.51	6.77	(8.26)
$\log K_{ML_2}$	5.11	(6.91)	5.52	(6.78)	6.17	5.03	(6.84)
$\log \beta_2$	11.90	(15.03)	11.96	(14.93)	12.68	11.80	(15.0)

* data are from ref. 4.

Fig. 3 represents a typical conductometric titration. The shape of the titration curve depends on the concentration and dissociation constants of the α -amino-oxy acid hydrobromide (H_2L^+). Rising salt concentrations produce an increase in the conductance. In consequence of these opposing influences, the titration curve may have a minima. The breaks at $a=1, 2, 3$ and 4 correspond to HL^+ , L^- , CuL^+ and CuL_2 , and confirm the existence of the complexes CuL^+ and CuL_2 in solution.

Results and Discussion

The pK values for α -amino-oxy acids are higher than those for the corresponding α -amino acids. Replacement of methylene hydrogen atoms in

Fig. 3. Conductometric curves (a) Titration of α -amino-oxy propionic acid hydrobromide (100 ml of $0.5 \times 10^{-3} M$) with $0.1 N$ NaOH solution. (b) Titration of α -amino-oxy propionic acid hydrobromide in presence of copper(II) Nitrate ($0.5 \times 10^{-3} M$) with $0.1 N$ NaOH solution.

α -amino acids produces a small but distinct increase in pK_1 and pK_2 . The same seems to be valid for α -amino-oxy acids. The pK_1 values for α -amino-oxy acetic acid however seems to be anomalous.

The pK_2 can be regarded as a measure of the basicity of α -oxy amino nitrogen. A comparison of the pK_2 values of the α -amino acids and corresponding α -amino-oxy acids show that α -amino-oxy nitrogen is more basic than α -amino nitrogen. There appears to be no simple relation between $\log K_{ML_2}$ and pK_2 ; indeed increase in basicity of nitrogen atom in L does not always produce an increase in the value of $\log K_{ML_2}$.

Similar results have been obtained by Irving and Pettit⁶ for the metal complexes of α -amino acids.

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